

Synthesis and Biological Properties of Some Basic N-(5-Aryl-1,3,4-Oxadiazol-2-yl) Propanamides and Butanamides*

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Some new basic N-(5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl) propanamides and butanamides have been synthesised by treating 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles with 3-chloropropanoyl chloride or 4-chlorobutanoyl chloride, respectively whereby 2-chloropropanamido- and 2-chlorobutanamido-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles resulted. These afforded the title compounds on subsequent treatment with various secondary amines. The hydrochlorides of almost all the compounds screened have shown considerable local anaesthetic activity.

THERAPEUTIC importance of oxadiazole moiety as analgesic^{1,5}, hypoglycemic², bactericidal^{3,4}, antipyretic⁵ and local anaesthetic, etc. has been studied. Literature reveals that derivatives of 2-aminobenzothiazole^{6,7}, 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole⁸⁻¹¹, 2-phenylamino-4-phenylthiazole¹² and 2-aminonaphthothiazole¹³ exhibit local anaesthetic activity. Keeping these in view, it was thought worthwhile to synthesize the title compounds with the presumption that they might have enhanced biological properties. The synthesis involves condensation of 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles with 3-chloropropanoyl chloride and 4-chlorobutanoyl chloride, respectively followed by condensation with morpholine, dimethylamine, diethylamine, dipropylamine, piperidine and pyrrolidine to afford the title compounds.

Experimental

Preparation of 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles: Different oxadiazoles were prepared by the method of Gibson¹⁴ by oxidative cyclization of appropriate aldehyde semicarbazones (0.05 M) with bromine (0.1M) and anhydrous sodium acetate (16 g) in glacial acetic acid.

Formation of 2-chloropropanamido- and 2-chlorobutanamido-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles: These compounds were synthesized by the method of Bhargava and Singh¹⁵.

2-Chloropropanamido-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles: Freshly distilled 3-chloropropanoyl chloride (0.01M) in dry benzene was added with constant stirring to a solution of 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (0.01M) containing potassium carbonate. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath at 70° for 2 hr. Excess benzene was distilled off and the residue was washed successively with sodium bicarbonate solution and water and finally recrystallized from ethanol. The compounds thus obtained are summarized in Table 1.

Following the similar procedure various 2-chlorobutanamido-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazole were prepared. These are summarized in Table 2.

TABLE 1—2-CHLOROPROPANAMIDO-5-ARYL-1,3,4-OXADIAZOLES

Sl. No.	R	Yield %	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)	
					C	N
1.	H	65	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂	211	52.32 (52.48)	16.63 (16.69)
2.	<i>o</i> -Chloro	60	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂	130	46.06 (46.15)	14.61 (14.68)
3.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	75	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	165	51.10 (51.16)	14.89 (14.92)
4.	<i>p</i> -Chloro	65	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂	172	46.08 (46.15)	14.59 (14.68)

TABLE 2—2-CHLOROBUTANAMIDO-5-ARYL-1,3,4-OXADIAZOLES

Sl. No.	R	Yield %	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)	
					C	N
1.	H	75	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	198	54.65 (54.24)	15.79 (15.82)
2.	<i>o</i> Chloro	63	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂	152	47.92 (48.00)	13.96 (14.00)
3.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	68	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	183	52.72 (52.79)	14.19 (14.21)
4.	<i>p</i> -Chloro	70	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂	168	47.89 (48.00)	13.92 (14.00)

The synthesized compounds were satisfactorily characterized by ir, elemental analyses and tlc. The ir spectra (in KBr) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. The spectra reveal character-

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ristic absorption bands in the region of 1738-1740, 1260 and 1340 cm^{-1} corresponding to C=O group, N=N=C linkage and pentacyclic ring, respectively. In addition, all the compounds exhibited a strong band around 1720-1670 cm^{-1} characteristic of C-N

group. Absorption bands in the region of 3230-3160 cm^{-1} indicated -NH- stretching frequency. The m.p.s. were taken in open glass capillaries and are uncorrected.

Formation of basic N-(5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl) propanamides and butanamides :

These compounds were synthesized by condensing secondary amines with various 2-chloropropanamido- and 2-chlorobutanamido-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles according to the method of Giri and Singh¹⁶.

Basic N-(5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl) propanamides : An ethanolic solution of appropriate secondary amine (0.1 M) was added to a solution of 2-chloropropanamido oxadiazole (0.5 M) in dry ethanol and the reaction mixture refluxed on a water bath for 6 hr at 72°. After the reaction, excess ethanol and amine were recovered by distillation and the residue was washed with sodium bicarbonate and water. The product was recrystallized from benzene. The

TABLE 3—BASIC N-(5-ARYL-1,3,4-OXADIAZOL-2-YL) PROPANAMIDES

Sl. No.	R	Yield %	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	m.p. of Hydrochlorides °C
R₁, R₂, N = Morpholine					
1.	H	75	242	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₃	286
2.	<i>o</i> -Chloro	68	171	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₃ Cl	213-214
3.	<i>p</i> -Chloro	65	237	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₃ Cl	258-259
4.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	70	228 ^d	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₄	241
R₁ - R₂ = Methyl					
5.	H	77	205	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃	230-231
6.	<i>o</i> -Chloro	60	195 ^d	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃ Cl	215-216
7.	<i>p</i> -Chloro	68	223	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃ Cl	283
8.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	72	192	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₄	272
R₁ - R₂ = Ethyl					
9.	H	70	231	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃	289-290
10.	<i>o</i> -Chloro	65	174	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃ Cl	208-209
11.	<i>p</i> -Chloro	59	182	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃ Cl	218
12.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	68	239 ^d	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₄	273
R₁ - R₂ = Propyl					
13.	H	68	202	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₃	223
14.	<i>o</i> -Chloro	72	191 ^d	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₃ Cl	253-254
15.	<i>p</i> -Chloro	70	186	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₃ Cl	263-264
16.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	62	198	C ₁₈ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₄	280
R₁, R₂, N = Piperidin					
17.	H	62	208	C ₁₈ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₃	273-274
18.	<i>o</i> -Chloro	68	163 ^d	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₃ Cl	219
19.	<i>p</i> -Chloro	60	171	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₃ Cl	278
20.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	73	177 ^d	C ₁₉ H ₂₅ N ₄ O ₄	210
R₁, R₂, N = Pyrrolidin					
21.	H	74	214	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₃	256-257
22.	<i>o</i> -Chloro	71	206 ^d	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₃ Cl	239-240
23.	<i>p</i> -Chloro	68	198 ^d	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₃ Cl	218
24.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	66	216	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₄	279-280

All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.
d - Melts with decomposition.

compounds thus prepared are summarized in Table 3. Following the similar procedure basic N-(5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl) butanamides were prepared. The compounds are recorded in Table 4. These compounds were characterized by ir spectra, m.p. and tlc. All the compounds were also analysed for N and S and gave satisfactory results.

TABLE 4—BASIC N-(5-ARYL-1,3,4-OXADIAZOL-2-YL) BUTANAMIDES

Sl. No.	R	Yield %	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	m.p. of Hydrochlorides °C
R₁, R₂, N = Morpholin					
1.	H	61	198	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₄	226
2.	<i>o</i> -Chloro	68	212	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄ Cl	253-254
3.	<i>p</i> -Chloro	72	186 ^d	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄ Cl	228-229
4.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	74	192	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₅	286
R₁ - R₂ = Methyl					
5.	H	72	191	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₄	232-233
6.	<i>o</i> -Chloro	62	215 ^d	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₄ Cl	286
7.	<i>p</i> -Chloro	68	223	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₄ Cl	293
8.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	73	236	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₅	278-279
R₁ - R₂ = Ethyl					
9.	H	58	232 ^d	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₄	249-250
10.	<i>o</i> -Chloro	62	199	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₄ Cl	207-208
11.	<i>p</i> -Chloro	65	192 ^d	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₄ Cl	228
12.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	71	188	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₅	256
R₁ - R₂ = Propyl					
13.	H	65	201	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₄	229-230
14.	<i>o</i> -Chloro	58	236	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₄ Cl	289
15.	<i>p</i> -Chloro	62	213	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₄ Cl	278
16.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	74	246 ^d	C ₁₈ H ₂₅ N ₄ O ₅	298
R₁, R₂, N = Piperidin					
17.	H	72	223	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ N ₄ O ₄	259
18.	<i>o</i> -Chloro	59	169	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₄ Cl	218
19.	<i>p</i> -Chloro	64	183 ^d	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₄ Cl	225-226
20.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	69	198	C ₁₈ H ₂₅ N ₄ O ₅	238-239
R₁, R₂, N = Pyrrolidin					
21.	H	64	218	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₄	251-252
22.	<i>o</i> -Chloro	67	224	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₄ Cl	238
23.	<i>p</i> -Chloro	70	212	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₄ Cl	259
24.	<i>p</i> -Methoxy	72	207	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₅	283

All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.
d - Melts with decomposition.

The ir spectra recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer showed characteristic absorption bands for -C-O-C-, -C=C- and -C=O groups in expected regions. The -C=O stretching frequency in 2-chloropropanamido- and 2-chlorobutanamido-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles appeared at a slightly higher value (55-95 cm^{-1}) as compared to the similar absorption band in basic oxadiazolyl propanamides and butanamides. This may be attributed to the greater electron attracting properties of α -chloro group than the -NR₁R₂ group.

The reaction may be depicted as in Scheme 1.

Biological screening :

The preliminary investigations on the local anaesthetic activity of hydrochlorides of the above bases showed considerable local anaesthetic activity by frog's sciatic plexus test. The local anaesthetic activity was also evaluated by employing surface

(R = H, *o*-Cl, *o*-OCH₃, *p*-Cl) (n = 2 or 3)
 (-NR₁R₂, -morpholino, dimethylamino, diethylamino, dipropylamino, piperidino, pyrrolidino)
 Scheme 1

anaesthesia on guinea pig cornea¹⁷ and intradermal anaesthesia (block anaesthesia) in guinea pig¹⁸. Other chemotherapeutic properties of these compounds are under investigation.

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